

New and Additional Records of Coreidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) fauna from Peru

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ABSTRACT: In the present study, two species are recorded from Peru (Coreidae). *Anasa fusca* Stål, 1870 is recorded for the first time from the country, whereas new locality information is provided for *Piezogaster rubropictus* (Montandon, 1897).

Anasa fusca, whose species description was based on 9 males and 16 females specimens is shortly redescribed.

KEY WORDS: : *Anasa fusca*, *Piezogaster rubropictus*, new faunistic records, Coreidae, Peru.

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INTRODUCTION

The family Coreidae Leach, 1815 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) includes four subfamilies, Coreinae Leach, 1815; Hydarinae Stål, 1873; Meropachyinae

Stål, 1868; and Pseudophloeinae Stål, 1868. It contains more than 2,600 species distributed among 450 genera worldwide, with around 1007 species and 165 genera distributed in the Nearctic and Neotropical regions. Coreinae is the

most common subfamily, represented by 32 tribes in both the Old and New World (Packauskas, 2010; Henry, 2017; Brailovsky & Perez-Gelabert, 2019; Pluot-Sigwalt & Moulet, 2022). Coreini contains 376 species belonging to 37 genera in the Nearctic and Neotropical regions (Brailovsky & Barrera, 2022). Juárez & González (2016) indicate that the Peruvian Coreidae fauna is poorly known, and only around 94 species of the Coreini were recorded.

Recent studies in the New World revealed the presence of 79 species belonging to the genus *Anasa* Amyot & Serville, 1843 (Coreinae: Coreini). Of those, the species *Anasa abdicata* Brailovsky, 1985, *A. apicalis* (Westwood, 1842), *A. bellator* (Fabricius, 1787), *A. byssoidecerus* Brailovsky & Barrera, 2009, *A. guayaquila* Brailovsky, 1985, *A. haglundii* Stål, 1870, *A. jucunda* Breddin, 1904, *A. marginella* Blöte, 1935, *A. micans* Brailovsky, 1985, *A. rectangulariformis* Brailovsky, 1985, *A. scorbutica* (Fabricius, 1775), *A. sibilica* Brailovsky, 1985, *A. sinuaticollis* Blöte, 1935 and *A. trilineata* Stål, 1870 are found in Peru. *Anasa marginella* and *A. rectangulariformis* are endemic to Peru (Brailovsky, 1985, 2016, 2017; Packauskas, 2010; Cruces & Vergara, 2015).

The tribe Nematopodini Amyot & Serville, 1843 (Leaf-footed bugs), which contains some of the largest species of Coreidae, contains 160 species belonging to 37 genera. Thirty three species belong to the genus *Piezogaster* Amyot & Serville, 1843 (Coreinae: Nematopodini).

Of those, *Piezogaster congruus* Brailovsky & Barrera, 1984, *Piezogaster dilatatus* (Dallas, 1852), *Piezogaster obscuratus* (Montandon, 1899), and *Piezogaster rubropictus* (Montandon, 1897) occur in Peru. *Piezogaster congruus* is endemic to Peru (Brailovsky & Barrera, 1983; Dealy, 2000; Packauskas, 2010; Juárez & González, 2016).

All Coreidae species are phytophagous and cause considerable damage to plants in both adult and nymphal stages.

Faunal records of countries, are very important for identifying agriculturally beneficial and harmful species, to develop control methods against harmful species, and identifying local and foreign species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The following abbreviation is used for the institution cited herein: Instituto de Biología, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, México City, México.

The specimens were collected with an entomological net in Aguas Calientes, Peru in 2018. For preparation of the genitalia, specimens were softened in hot water and their genitalia extracted using forceps. Genitalia of males and females were examined using a Leica SZX stereoscopic microscope and body Canon 70D, ring flash, 69mm. Macro tube T, Canon 100mm. IS USM 2.8L. Keys and descriptions from Brailovsky (1985; 2016) and Cruces (2013) were used to identify the specimens.

RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

Family Coreidae Leach, 1815

Subfamily Coreinae Leach, 1815

Tribe Coreini Leach, 1815

Anasa Amyot & Serville, 1843

Anasa fusca Stål, 1870

Material examined. Peru: Cusco region: Aguas Calientes, 24.01.2018, 2161 masl, 1♂, (leg. A. Dursun; det. H. Brailovsky).

Distribution in Peru: New record from Peru.

Distribution in Neotropic Region: Colombia, Surinam, Venezuela (Packauskas, 2010).

Host plant. Unknown.

Redescription of male: (Figure 1 a-h). Dorsal coloration (Figure 1a). Head yellowish brown with black pitting (Figure 1a, c). Length of head 1.5mm. Diatone 1.8mm. Rostrum brownish yellow reaching

middle coxa (Figure 1b). Antennae yellow with short yellowish hairs, distally and proximally of four antennal segment black. Lengths of antennae segments I-V (mm): 1.2, 2.0, 1.99, 1.7. (Figure 1d). Pronotum blackish brown, proximal corners of pronotum black (Figure 1c). Length of pronotum 2.8 mm. and pronotum width 5 mm.

Pronotum, scutellum and hemelytra with yellowish hairs. Membrane light brown. Connexivum blackish brown, distally and proximally yellow. Dorsum brownish yellow. Bucculae yellow with brown pitting. Pectus and abdominal ventral surface brown with black pitting (Figure 1b).

Peritreme of scent gland ostiole widened and oval apically, laterally corrugated with yellowish tubercle (Figure 1e). Legs yellow, distally of femur brown. Femur and tibia brownish pitting (Figure 1b). Pygophore yellow with black pitted and yellowish hairs, the ventral rim of pygophore shallow incised medially (Figure 1f). Blade of paramere slightly rounded dorsally, towards tip nearly straight (Figure 1 g, h). Total length 12.5 mm.

Tribe Nematopodini Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Piezogaster* Amyot & Serville, 1843**

***Piezogaster rubropictus* (Montandon, 1897)** (Figure 2 a, b, c, d, e)

Material examined. Peru: Cusco region: Aguas Calientes, 24.01.2018, 2161 masl. 4♀♀, 2♂♂ (leg. & det. A. Dursun).

Distribution in Peru: Pazuzu (As *Capaneus (Leptoxuthus) rubropictus*) (Blöte, 1938).

Distribution in Neotropic Region: Boliva, Ecuador, Peru (Blöte, 1938; Packauskas, 2010).

Host plant: The specimens were collected on an unidentified Solanaceae species (Figure 2c).

This study contributed to knowledge of

the Peruvian Coreidae fauna. In particular, *Anasa fusca*, a species that causes significant damage to both wild plants and cultivated cucurbits, and is one of the most economically important species, has been recorded for the first time for Peruvian fauna. Thus, the number of Peruvian *Anasa* species has been increased to 15 species. In addition, according to records made by Staudinger in 1932, *Piezogaster rubropictus* species cited in Peru is the second record. *Piezogaster rubropictus* was cited by Blöte (1938) as *Capaneus (Leptoxuthus) rubropictus* in Pazuzu, Peru, but there are no records from any other peruvian locality.

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Figure 1. *Anasa fusca* Stål, 1870 (male). a) Dorsal view, b) Ventral view, c) Pronotum and scutellum, d) Antennae, e) Evaporatorium surface, f) Pygophore, g-h) Paramere.

Figure 2. *Piezogaster rubropictus* (Montandon, 1897) a) Male (Dorsal view), b) Female (Dorsal view), c) Host plant, d) Pygophore (Lateral view), e) Paramere.